

Institutional Choice, Semi-loyal Political Parties, and the Trajectory of Political Polarization in Albania

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Introduction

This paper posits that an inquiry into the historical context and initial political dynamics of regime transition must be made to understand the factors that have influenced the stable features of a polarized two-bloc party system in post-communist Albania. Despite short-term political compromises and restrictive issue-based elite pacts between key representatives of the Democratic Party and the Socialist Party, mainly conditioned and encouraged by external actors, such as the European Union, polarization has remained a constant feature of political competition and rhetoric between the two main blocs, and political parties. The institutional choices, and the lack thereof, during the political and economic transition from December 1990 until March 1992 constitute the critical juncture shaping the political competition process between the Democratic Party and the Socialist Party (ex-communists), the two leading contenders for power. The confrontational and adversarial political competition took place under conditions of “stalemated transition” (McFaul 2002, p. 234), characterized by “protracted confrontation and imposition” (2002, p. 234). As most scholars say, regime transitions entail practices of institutional design, which in the case of post-communist societies involves, at the same time, economic and political transition (Elster, Offe, & Preuss, 1998). Due to the absence of a sustained anti-regime political movement, mainly as a consequence of the Stalinist nature of the communist regime, despite the limited and insufficient liberalizing reforms of the late 1980s that granted more autonomy to the socialist intelligentsia (Biberaj 1987), the first opposition party, namely the Democratic Party of Albania (hereafter DP) and its leadership were quite uncertain about its social base or linkages to a stable constituency. Alternatively, to say it differently, the heterogeneity and conflicting dimensions of the social base of the first opposition party (DP) made the constituencies of that party more malleable to the political competition strategies of the key political representatives. Contrary to the general assumption, the founding members of the Democratic Party, depicted as a “small cadre of the political elite” (Amy and Gjermeni, 2013, p. 9), which shows their lack of roots in the society, had different strategies of electoral mobilization and political competition. One faction, which could be termed the liberal faction of the DP, opted for a political competition with the Socialist Party (ex-communists, hereafter SP) based on differences in economic policies. The other faction, which could be termed the anti-communist conservative faction, sought to mobilize the regime divide, emphasizing the cultural dimension of political competition.

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Henceforth, the trajectory of the political polarization in post-communist Albania unfolds once the institutionalization of the party system takes shape and the DP suffers a marginal yet pivotal electoral setback after the first local elections of 1992 and the referendum on the constitution in 1994, when contrasted to the overwhelming majority it obtained in March 1992. According to Moraes and Béjar (2022, p. 3), “as electoral volatility increases the risks of electoral survival, polarization becomes an efficient strategy to mobilize voters ...” Albeit the electoral setbacks of the DP do not reflect steep electoral volatility in the party system, they increased the uncertainty of the future electoral success of the Democratic Party in the upcoming electoral contests. This contingency made the leadership of the Democratic Party pursue and deepen political polarization.

Thus, the polarized political competition is enabled by the legacy of the regime transition in post-communist Albania, which could be characterized as lacking substantial and consensual “power-sharing arrangements...then institutionalized as a set of checks and balances in the new democracy” (McFaul 2002, p. 213). The process of political and economic transition in post-communist Albania did not follow either a social mobilization of the opposition movement that made the communist regime in Czechoslovakia yield to the demands of the opposition or a pact transition between moderates and soft-liners prior to electoral contestation (McFaul 2002, p. 216) as in Poland and Hungary. Instead, the institutional choice was subjected to the electoral fortunes of the main competitors, namely the DP and the SP, in the first and second parliamentary elections, and as such, the “benefit of transition [was not] ...shared” (2002, p. 222). The political and economic reforms after the 1991 elections won by the Party of Labor of Albania (hereafter PLA), with a considerable presence and popular support of the DP in the urban centers, were piecemeal outcomes of shifting majorities in the parliament formed mainly by the moderates of both political parties. However, in the first parliamentary election, neither political party was hegemonic, which led to a stalemate transition making the “design of constitutional institutions..., [that] often involve distributional effects” (McFaul 1999, p. 33) unstable and subject to instrumentalization. The parliament’s approval of the so-called constitutional package constituted after the 1991 elections was deemed provisional. The reversal of the electoral fortunes in favor of the DP in the 1992 anticipatory elections, under the absence of a shared constitutional foundation of the new regime and constraints on the executive, provided a leeway for the DP to erode the existing political regime towards a hybrid political regime. The Democratic Party drifted to a semi-loyal political party and actor, manifesting political actions and decisions that were anti-pluralist by not recognizing the SP as a legitimate contender in the newly emerging party system. The political polarization between the DP and the SP intensified as the post-communist political regime became more authoritarian.

The economic reforms, including the privatization of small and medium state enterprises, during the first government of the DP, were characterized by clientelism (Case, 2000; Gërçhani & Schram, 2009). Establishing market economy institutions, particularly property rights and financial institutions, proved as daunting and unsuccessful as constitutional institutions. Political polarization was manifested socially into a divided society of two distinct social bases for the semi-loyal political parties. The DP’s social base started to include mostly those voters and social groups that manifested an affective polarization related to an anti-communist cultural identity not reconcilable with the SP’s political identity and those voters that forged clientelist linkages with the DP officeholders benefiting from economic transition. The SP’s social base included mostly those voters that had an ambiguous stance, if not nostalgia, towards the ancien régime responsive to affective polarization that was not reconcilable first and foremost with the DP’s political identity and those voters who experienced downward social mobility and even administrative purges due to the economic and political reforms of the DP. It is not mere happenstance that the first wave of political polarization led to the breakdown of the political system and state

institutions, an adverse effect of polarization emphasized by most scholars (Huntington 1968; Linz 1978). The two leading contenders for power and their respective party blocs became entangled in a polarized party system in the mid-1990s.

2. An explanatory model of political polarization and its trajectory

Usually, the recent upsurge in political polarization in Western Europe and the US has been attributed to the rising influence of radical right or radical left parties (de Vries and Hobolt 2020; Hausermann & Kriesi 2015; Hooghe and Marks 2018 quoted in Borbath, Hutter, & Leininger, 2023) established by “political entrepreneurs – especially from the populist radical right - ... mobilizing issues of order and belonging tapping into conflicts about national identity, sovereignty and solidarity” (Borbath, Hutter, & Leininger 2023). In contrast, political polarization in post-communist East Central Europe is instigated by mainstream political parties that have shown dubious or no substantive normative commitments to liberal democracy (Herman 2015, p. 254), undermining institutional checks and balances. On the other hand, the expected positive effect of a stable party system institutionalization in consolidating a democratic regime according to the rational-institutional approach (Herman 2015, p. 256) has been transfigured into a “party-centered electoral democracy within which one of the established parties systematically drains the resources of its rivals and weakens the power of checks and balances” (Enyedi 2016, 218). In some instances, and at specific periods in time, the political competition between political parties is characterized by “populist polarization,” as exemplified by the case study of Hungary (Enyedi 2016). Notwithstanding the presence of “aggressive competition between party blocs, [and] concomitant rejection of the division of power” (Enyedi 2016, p. 217), which one finds in the case study of Albania, populist electoral strategies have not been quite dominant. More specifically, the dynamics of political polarization, as this paper argues, in the case of Albania are due to structural features of regime transition that led to partial democratization (McFaul 2002) rather than a consequence of democratic erosion after the consolidation of democracy as in Hungary and Poland (Bernhard, 2021; Enyedi 2016; Enyedi 2020, Simon and Bozóki 2019). Markus Wagner (2020), proposing a different approach to affective polarization in a multiparty system, observes that its mean distance measure “capturing how much an individual on average dislikes other parties compared to his or her favored party” (2021, p. 16) for countries such as Albania or Montenegro is relatively high, bearing in mind that these countries are “less stable democracies” (Wagner 2020, p. 18). Henceforth, understanding the sources and trajectory of the political polarization in the case of unconsolidated democracies such as Albania, vacillating from competitive authoritarian regimes to electoral democracy, seems to require a different theoretical model.

The process of institutional choice under conditions of uncertainty during a regime transition is predicated on the balance of forces between the ancien régime’s soft-liners and the opposition’s moderates (O’Donnell et al., 1986), while both parties are facing pressure from the radicals in their respective groupings. Empirical evidence suggests that “a relatively equal distribution of power between major actors” (McFaul 1999, p. 27) does not always lead to “compromise and reconciliation between all sides” (1999, p. 27). The centrality of institutional choice during regime transition involves establishing foundational and necessary institutional constraints “to jugulate the threats of unregulated competition” (Herman 2015, p. 255). These institutional constraints come in the form of “... power-sharing arrangements negotiated during the transition then institutionalized as a set of checks and balances in the new democracy” (McFaul 2002, p. 213). However, in some post-communist countries, regime transition did not involve substantial consensus-based power-sharing arrangements or elite pacts (McFaul 2002, p. 221). Regime transitions in which the contending major groups and parties had equal power, meaning that neither the opposition nor the representatives of the ancien régime were hegemonic in the first parlia-

mentary elections, led to a stalemate. A protracted transition leads to a partial democratization (McFaul 2002). Thus, the absence of genuine institutionalized checks and balances agreed upon by the major contenders for dominance in the post-authoritarian regime constitutes a structural feature of the emerging political competition between the opposition and reformed communists. If institutional choices are piecemeal and provisional in terms of their endurance and effect, then the incumbents of the next elections would instrumentally and selectively use or “invest in the new institutional order, which in turn provides increasing returns” (McFaul 2002, p. 32) without properly institutionalizing checks and balances.

Another facet of the transition process is the interaction between the emerging political society and the civil society. Borrowing from Linz and Stepan’s (1996) understanding of political and civil society and their interaction, one could argue that in those post-communist transitions in which the boundaries between the civil society and the political society are not clearly demarcated and the emerging grass-rooted civil society does not appear to function as a bulwark to the political society, political violence, mobilizations outside of the institutional arena and a zero-sum game between the contending parties for power are not precluded. Linz and Stepan (1996, p. 3) attribute to a “robust civil society ...the capacity to generate political alternatives and to monitor government and state, *can help start transitions, help resist reversal, help push transitions to their completion*, and help consolidate and deepen democracy” (italics are mine). On the other hand, political society is defined as “...that arena in which political actors compete for the legitimate right to exercise control over public power and the state apparatus” (Linz and Stepan 1996, p. 3). Although the concept of political society includes a diverse set of political institutions such as the legislature, electoral rules, and political parties, according to the authors, the focus will be on political parties primarily. According to Linz and Stepan (1996, p.3), a defining feature of the practice within political society is a compromise between contending political parties. While Linz and Stepan (1996) talk about the complementarity of civil society with the political society, the case study of Albania shows a conflation between the two or in which the political society dominates over the civil society. These features of the regime transition legacy enable political entrepreneurs of one of the main political parties or blocs to trigger, unconstrained yet not predetermined, a process of political polarization dynamic in conditions of the contingency and initial uncertainty of political competition.

The political and economic transition after the fall of the dictatorship produces distinct categories of subjectivities, distinct from the subjectivities and social groups of the past regime or the resurfacing of subjectivities that were dormant during the dictatorship (Kajsiu, 2010, p. 230). The political competition between the representatives of the opposition and the representatives of the past regime, which have reformed themselves into social democrats (Bozóki & Ishiyama, 2003; Grzymala-Busse, 2002), is structured under conditions of initial “dealignment...as a departure point” (Enyedi 2008, p. 297 quoted in Casal-Bértoa 2014). The institutionalization of the party system after regime change, which is transformed into a “polarized party system” (McCoy et al., 2018, p. 17), as in the case study of Albania, has entailed the mobilization of particular social groups and subjectivities after a period of uncertainty about the social base of the post-communist political parties. As Kajsiu (2010, p. 247) argues throughout the article and in an extensive footnote, the main opposition party, the Democratic Party of Albania (DP), was far more uncertain about its social base than the Socialist Party (ex-communists). On the other hand, one need not assume that the emerging political parties, particularly the opposition party, were a homogeneous group sharing a coherent ideology. The existence of distinct fractions within the opposition party, with a liberal cosmopolitan faction and a conservative-nationalist faction and the competition for ideological dominance made it uncertain whether the opposition was representing disaffected workers that organized strikes against the dictatorship during the transition period,

the politically persecuted and the inter-war property owners who had been marginalized and cast as a pariah external to the social reproduction of the state socialist social formation (Lleshi, 2020), or the urban communities that manifested anti-regime stances rather than a traditional anti-communist ideology.

The paper contends that the establishment of a polarized party system and its trajectory in Albania is a consequence of the critical juncture of regime transition featuring few if any, institutional constraints and a conflation between the political society and the civil society triggering a specific path dependency of a polarized party system when political parties and intra-party factions give shape to the political competition. The trajectory of political polarization changes in intensity, which seem to be associated with the move from initial partial democratization to a competitive authoritarian regime (McCoy et al., 2018, p. 20) in the mid-1990s or reinforced by the political and economic crisis. As the political competition between the DP and the SP dominates the party system, the contending political parties could have emphasized and mobilized diverse types of cleavages as distinctive of the political divide in the post-transition period. While initially, in the very first years of the regime transition, both the DP and the SP provided similar “issue-oriented cues” (Hetherington, 2001, p. 621) to the citizens regarding the “post-communist divide” (Casal-Bértoa 2014, p. 21) making for a short stint, the post-communist cleavage a cross-cutting cleavage, they differed in terms of how radical the economic reforms would be (Kajsiu, 2016, p. 289). However, the divide between the political elite in the communist past widens because “political entrepreneurs effectively highlight and activate underlying cleavages in the society, ...constructing a dominant cleavage” (McCoy et al. 2018, p. 18). The trajectory of political polarization starts when the “distribution of the cleavage structures” (Casal-Bértoa 2014, p. 22) changes, making the cultural cleavage (post-communist divide) the dominant one. Thus, the concept of political polarization, initially an elite-led process and based on a cumulative cleavage, provided by McCoy et al., is more appropriate: “...a process whereby the normal multiplicity of differences in the society increasingly align along a single dimension, cross-cutting differences become reinforcing” (2018, p. 18). Albeit the fact that distinct social identities and subjectivities had already emerged during or prior to the political competition and the institutionalization of the party system, such as the social group of the politically persecuted under the dictatorship, it took the political elites to mobilize this cultural divide and transform it into a dominant one. Henceforth, political polarization is initiated by the political elite, followed by solid party identification at the mass level responding to the political parties’ frames of the dominant policy issue(s) (Druckman, Peterson, & Slothuus, 2013, p. 60). Due to the relational nature of polarization (McCoy et al., 2018, p. 18), supporters, partisans, and groups who perceive access to the material benefits, due to clientelistic economic reforms, as a zero-sum game (Hetherington 2001, p. 624), develop affective polarization through time (Bosco & Verney, 2020; Markus, 2021). I posit that the continuity of the political polarization, despite the waning of certain political divisions that initially mobilized polarization, is maintained due to a “polarizing rhetoric” (McCoy et al., 2018, p. 21) and the presence of “polarizing figures” (Bosco & Verney 2020, p. 266).

The behavior of the political parties that start the process of political polarization, or those that get embroiled in such an antagonistic inter-party interaction, is another critical factor of the dynamic of political polarization. As Herman (2015, p. 266) points out, political polarization implies specific strategies of mobilization and a non-democratic “content of party competition” (2015, p. 266). Henceforth, the anti-pluralistic polarizing rhetoric and behavior of a major political party, questioning the entitlement and right of the opponent to rule (see Enyedi 2016, p. 213), and the disinclination to foster compromise and cooperation make scholars of political polarization categorize such political parties as “expressing loyalty or disloyalty to the democratic norms” (Linz 1978, 28-38, quoted in Herman 2015, p. 272). A weak and incipient civil society during

the early years of regime transformation, dominated by an emerging political society (Chiodi 2012, p. 6), whose actors are not rooted in social groups, makes leaders of the political parties be “driven by the desire to acquire more power and likely to seize any available opportunity to do so” (Herman 2015, p. 264). Gunther and Diamond (2003) provide a helpful conceptualization of distinguishing between conflicting “strategies and behavioral norms of the party, whether the party is pluralistic or proto-hegemonic in its objectives and behavioral style” (p. 171). The parties that show pluralist behavior are: “fully committed to democratic rules of the game, are tolerant and respectful towards their opponents, and are pluralistic in their views of polity and society” (Gunther & Diamond 2003, p. 171). The political parties that start a process of political polarization express an ambiguous and lower degree of commitment to the democratic rules of the game, less tolerance towards the opponents, and an exclusive view of a polity. However, they are not “explicitly anti-system, favoring the replacement of the existing pluralistic democracy with a regime that would be more uniformly committed to the achievement of their programmatic objectives” (2003, p. 171). Hence, I consider these kinds of parties semi-loyal parties. This notion applies even to the mainstream opposition political parties, which, albeit being initially committed to democratic norms, facing an incumbent political party undermining further the democratic institutions and polarizing the political competition, respond using the same non-democratic strategies and norms. Another category of a political party that engaged in an equally non-democratic strategy and behavior during the trajectory of the political polarization in Albania is the category of “anti-political establishment party” (Schedler 1996). According to Schedler (1996, p. 293), anti-political establishment parties structure politics as an antagonistic interaction between “the political class, the people and themselves” (293). Moreover, they can position themselves “as acting outside the party system and ...having to construct an anti-political identity” (1996, p. 298). This type of political party is equally disinclined towards compromise, cultivating tolerance or recognition of the opponent as much as a mainstream party pursues a polarizing strategy and has a less inclusive understanding of the political system.

The first section below presents and analyzes the sources and trajectory of the political polarization in Albania. The timeline includes the first years of the regime transition, 1991-1992, that constitute the critical juncture enabling political entrepreneurs within the dominant political parties to structure a polarizing political competition and deepen the polarization when acting in “electoral settings [that are] unstable [as] developing democracies” (Moraes and Béjar 2022, p. 2). The second section delineates the deepening of political polarization during 1994-1997, leading to the establishment of a competitive authoritarian regime and the mechanisms that reinforced and normalized political polarization from 1998-2003. A third section presents the change in the trajectory of political polarization due to the role of the transformation of a mainstream political party into an anti-political establishment party. A separate section discusses a brief period of waning political polarization replaced by a more programmatic political competition and cooperative strategies between the leading contenders for power.

3. Trajectories of Political Polarization in Albania

3.1 Legacies of regime transition – 1991- 1992

The regime transition in Albania focused on delineating and establishing a political society understood in restrictive terms, including the legalization and recognition of political parties besides the PLA. Student protests took place in December 1990, after “thousands of [people stormed] Western embassies in Tirana seeking asylum, while thousands more commanded rusty boats in Durrës harbor and fled to Italy” (Fischer 2010, p. 423), demanded the right to establish political parties distinct from the ruling party of the regime and yet within a somewhat simi-

lar discursive space excluding radical, fascist and parties of reactionary-conservative persuasion. Meanwhile, the general secretary of the PLA, with the functions of the president of the presidium of the popular assembly (a state socialist terminology for a non-bourgeois rubber-stamp parliament), informed the students in an official and televised meeting that the Central Committee of the PLA had decided to legalize political pluralism. The DP, established on the 12th of December 1990, had a limited and generic political platform “but based generally on democracy, a market economy and national reconciliation” (Fischer 2010, p. 423). The DP, in the beginning, besides the appeals to free the political prisoners and positioning itself in favor of reconciliation regarding the historical injustice of the past regime, did not present a coherent conceptualization of an institutional and constitutional design. Thus, there were no official elite pact or negotiations between the opposition and the soft-liners of the outgoing regime about a shared institutional choice of the post-communist regime.

On the other hand, the first years of the transition and the economic crisis that ensued were characterized by the breakdown of the social order (Kajsiu 2010, p. 235), during which “people took revenge of the state through the destruction of state property, including government offices and schools” (Fischer 2010, 423). At this critical juncture of political and economic reforms, the state was disinvested in its welfare functions (Amy & Gjermeni 2013, p. 17), laying off workers and shutting industrial enterprises down (Muço 1997, 20). The emerging civil society’s incipient organizational units and associations included a Human Rights Forum and an Independent Trade Union external to the official trade union. The opposition DP obtained as a concession from the ruling party of the outgoing regime the deferral of the first parliamentary elections from February 1991 to 31st of March 1991. The outcome of these elections showed a resilient PLA (transformed into a social-democratic party in June 1991) that won two-thirds of the parliamentary majority and an equally robust opposition rooted in the urban centers (Åslund & Sjöberg 1992, p. 139). The communists, albeit dominated by a more reformist faction, formed the cabinet in April. The result of the elections triggered a series of protests and riots in the urban centers dominated by the opposition (Åslund & Sjöberg 1992, p. 138). Thus, neither the communists nor the opposition was in a hegemonic position to decide the outcome of the institutional choice after the first parliamentary elections.

Initially, the opposition (DP) interpreted the electoral results of March 1991 due to the support of diverse “subjectivities” and social groups “Our party won the support of the workers, the youth, intellectuals, and the most emancipated sectors of the society” (1991). The social category of the politically persecuted was not identified yet as a relevant social base of the DP, also because of a delayed release of all political prisoners so that they would not stand for the 31st of March 1991 elections. The DP leadership refused to participate in a power-sharing agreement with the PLA after the elections, which consisted of a coalition government. The association of the independent trade unions, slowly affiliating with the DP, organized a general strike, which led to the downfall of the PLA’s government in June 1991. Then, the DP agreed to enter a coalition government with the PLA controlling influential ministerial portfolios, especially those in charge of the economic reforms (Åslund & Sjöberg 1992, p. 138). Despite its inclusion in a limited power-sharing agreement, the DP used “political mobilization as a constant political strategy,” and it withdrew from the coalition government in December 1991. A rift emerged within the DP between a more liberal faction aiming to structure the political competition with the Socialist Party (ex-communists) along the socio-economic divide and a conservative-nationalist faction spearheaded by Berisha downplaying the economic cleavage and programmatic competition.

The economic reforms implemented during those six months by the coalition government between the DP and the SP dealt primarily with liberalization, so-called Land reform, which granted land to “former members of the cooperatives, turning them into farmers” (Kajsiu 2010,

p. 436), and the privatization of small-scale privatization (Muço 1997, p. 19). However, it did not reconstitute property to the expropriated property owners by the communist dictatorship. As Muço (1997) argues, the coalition government between the two main competitors did not establish effective and consensus-based market institutions. Regarding political institutions, the DP receded from its first position in favor of parliamentary democracy, with a “strong parliament and weak president” (Report, 1991). Instead, after the electoral outcome of the March 1991 elections, the DP endorsed a limited and provisional constitutional package that emphasized mainly “political pluralism and freedom of religion, guaranteed human and civil rights” (Fischer 2010, p. 424), which was approved in parliament with the support of the PLA’s reformist group within its parliamentary majority (Biberaj 1999). After the March 1991 elections, the parliament elected Ramiz Alia, former general secretary of the PLA and a pivotal actor in the regime transition, as president of the republic. The DP did not put forward an opposition candidate to the candidacy of the PLA. However, the office of the president during the short stint of Alia, who resigned in April 1992 after the DP won the anticipatory elections of the 22nd of March 1992, cast a long shadow on the functioning of the political system even though its constitutional powers were not formalized in the provisional limited constitutional package. Henceforth, the DP or crucial political entrepreneurs within the opposition party’s leadership were less institutionally constrained once they won the March 1992 parliamentary elections and pursued a strategy of political polarization during their first governing mandate.

3.2 The dominance of cultural cleavage, pivotal electoral setbacks: The trajectory and intensity of political polarization 1992-1997

In March 1992 parliamentary elections, the second ones after regime change, the opposition won a landslide victory as a coalition between the DP, the Social-Democratic Party of Albania (initially presenting itself as the genuine center-left party compared to the SP) and the Republic Party. However, the DP itself was short of a constitutional majority. The Democratic Party entered the 1992 parliamentary elections with not a clearly defined social base or electoral constituency. The splinter parties created during the first governing mandate of the DP, in the years 1992 to 1993, show distinct and contradictory ideological projects within the Democratic Party. The first splinter party that exited the DP, a centrist liberal party, was established by the liberal faction of the DP. Key representatives of this faction emphasized in the print media, primarily in their party newspaper, the multi-dimensionality of political competition with a legitimate contender as the Socialist Party. “We are better prepared than the Socialist Party. We should show that we not only know which the main paths of development are but also that we should indicate the manners through which we shall attain these crucial components of democracy” (Pashko, 1991, the 12th of October). Another representative of this faction downplays the dominance of the cultural (post-communist) divide, aiming to constrain its harmful consequences to society at large “Anti-communism is necessary in Albania, but that should not lead us to civil war. We aspire to become European” (Rilindja Demokratike, 1991). The second splinter party was founded in 1993 by a more radical anti-communist faction that objected to the Land Reform of 1991 and supported full restitution of property to the expropriated property owners by the dictatorship (Kajsiu 2010, p. 236). The Democratic Party, dominated by Berisha, to use the terminology of McCoy et al. (2018), homogenized the party from within by “[not] allowing any internal dissent within the party” (Fischer 2010, p. 427). As Kajsiu argues, the DP “... [could] not satisfy the various social groups it aimed to represent” (2010, p. 235). This led to a polarizing rhetoric stemming from “the emergence of the anti-communist discourse” (Kajsiu 2010, p. 235).

The polarization dynamic took shape and deepened in intensity due to the electoral setback experienced by the DP in the local elections of July 1992 and the constitutional referendum of

1994. “After an electoral loss in July 1992 local elections, the DP started prosecuting the leader of the opposition SP, Fatos Nano, who was eventually arrested in 1993 and sentenced to twelve years on corruption charges (Kajsiu 2010, p. 238). The post-communist divide became the dominant policy issue of the public discourse and political competition of the DP in power. The other policy issues, such as anti-corruption or economic reforms, were subsumed into the dominant cultural cleavage. During its government, the DP pursued “wide-ranging purges... in all of the ministries” (Fischer 2010, p. 425). These purges also affected the judiciary system inherited from the state socialist dictatorship.

To some extent, political regimes that move away from an authoritarian one face the complex dilemma of ensuring the state bureaucracy’s loyalty to the new democratic regime. However, there is not just one solution to this dilemma; neither is the one imposed unilaterally by the DP the only solution. The lack of checks and balances and the institutional constraints enabled the DP to succeed in instigating a polarized party system. Especially after the loss in the constitutional referendum (Fischer 2010, p. 428), which sought the approval of the citizens for “further augment[ing] the power of the president” (p. 428), the DP intensified the polarization between the DP and the main opposition SP. The DP became a semi-loyal political party that did not recognize the legitimacy or the right of the center-left opposition (SP) to govern if democratically elected. The opposition’s candidates, primarily those of the SP, were disqualified from participating in the 1996 parliamentary elections due to specific politicized transitional justice measures such as the ‘Genocide Law’ of 1995. By misrecognizing the SP as not entitled to govern in a democracy, the DP “increasingly emphasized the communist menace to democracy and freedom against which society...and the electoral base of the DP could be held together” (Kajsiu 2010, p. 235). As Figure 1 shows, political polarization increased after the 1994 constitutional referendum and peaked in 1996-1997.

The distribution of material goods to supporters and loyalists of the party during the privatization process proved to be effective in enhancing the partisan identification of the social base of the DP by making them perceive access to material goods and benefits as a zero-sum game. As Gërxxhani and Schram (2000) posit, “... the privatization process was also used by the democratic government to increase its popularity through various economic and political favors to individuals, strata and social groups” (p. 4). In a separate article, Gërxxhani and Schram (2009) show that clientelism in a polarized political system reinforces the existing political polarization. The mechanism through which clientelism reinforces polarization, according to the authors, is: “Because of the numerous ways the party helps them and is expected to keep on helping them, their votes are not affected by specific (e.g., economic) outcomes of ...policies” (2009, p. 309). As Figure 2 shows, practices of clientelism in the political system after regime change was associated with a big score of exclusion by political groups, primarily during the first mandate of the Democratic Party.

The embroilment of the opposition SP into the polarized political system transformed the SP into a semi-loyal political party as well, willing to concede to political violence and strategies of obstructive opposition in the face of a competitive authoritarian regime. The SP boycotted the electoral precinct boards in the 1996 parliamentary elections, which inaugurated a series of contested and flawed elections (Fischer 2010, p. 436). The SP opposition boycotted parliament after the 1996 parliamentary elections. The financial crisis, triggered by the collapse of the pyramid schemes (Jarvis 1999), led to protests and riots, mainly in the south of the country, where most of the strongholds of the SP were situated (Fischer 2010). More specifically, the SP, while in opposition, opted to take advantage of “this crisis...to finally get rid of Berisha (Fischer 2010, p. 430). To some extent, the “involvement of high-ranking SP officials” (Fischer 2010, p. 430) in the violent riots, and the role of “disaffected former military and secret police officers,” constituting

a part of the social base of the SP, (p. 430) in putting up the resistance to representatives of state institutions, indicate the shift of the SP towards a semi-loyal political party. The international community mediated a political agreement between the DP and the SP leading to a national reconciliation coalition government that intends to restore order and prepare for the anticipatory parliamentary elections of 1997. Because of this political agreement and of

the centralized nature of the DP still run by Berisha, the former president remained in politics as a polarizing figure for the opposing camp.

Figure 1

Source: V-Dem Polarization Index (Data version 13)

3.3 Mechanism of normalizing political polarization 1998-2003: Polarizing figures, rhetoric and contested electoral outcomes

Although the intensity of political polarization abated after 1997, political polarization was not replaced by a more consensus-based and cooperative strategy between the main political parties. The SP coalition government pursued the same practice of administrative purges after the 1997 electoral victory as the DP is now in opposition. “Subsequent changes of government inevitably produced changes in every layer of the public administration as the SP and the DP rewarded supporters and punished public servants identified with the other side” (O’Brennan & Gassie 2009, p. 72). The DP pursued a strategy of obstructive opposition by boycotting the parliament after the 1997 elections, which was dubbed as “the parliament of the Kalashnikovs” (Fischer 2010, p. 435). On the other hand, the DP did not participate in the deliberations on the constitutional draft, which was approved by a referendum in November 1998. The internally weak and less ideologically diverse political parties led to stagnation in the political elite and not elite circulation at the apex of the party leadership. The endurance, by any means, of the political leadership, who were the first instigators as political entrepreneurs of political polarization, transformed them into

Figure 2

Source: V-Dem data version 13

polarizing figures. This is one of the persistent mechanisms of normalizing political polarization, which has been less successfully upended. The polarizing figure of Berisha had a mobilizing effect on the voters of the SP and vice versa, the polarizing figure of Nano for the voters of the DP.

Nevertheless, for a polarizing figure to have a mobilizational appeal to the opposing party, it requires polarizing rhetoric and an already sedimented affective polarization among the supporters and voters of each of the main contending parties. After the 1997 parliamentary elections, the DP and its party leadership "...escalated the usual invective by frequently referring to Nano as a criminal and a drug addict, while the DP militants often degenerated into terrorist gangs (Fischer 2010, p. 435). On the other hand, in its polarizing rhetoric during the 2005 electoral campaign, the SP instrumentally used Berisha's polarizing figure to contain a probable electoral defeat. "In the 2005 general elections campaign, the SP focused almost exclusively on the leader of the opposition Berisha as a threat to the future of Albania" (Kajsiu 2010, p. 242). The fact that the ideological distance between the SP and the DP, at least regarding the economic policies and EU integration policy issue (Kajsiu 2013, p. 1019), was reduced did not make the political competition less polarizing.

During this period, the parliamentary elections of 2001 and the local elections of 2000 and 2003 were bitterly contested (Fischer 2010). "None of these elections fully measured up to international standards, giving the opposition the reason to question not only the legitimacy of the ballots but also that of the governments they produced" (Fischer 2010, p. 436). Henceforth, it could be argued that the political polarization between the two-party blocs made it difficult to hold free and fair elections. The continuous presence of flawed and contested elections reinforced political polarization. The weighted mean distance measure of affective polarization for Albania, which "captures how much an individual on average dislikes other parties compared to his or her favored party" (Markus 2021, p. 15-16), is roughly above 6 when the range is from 0-8, one

can posit that affective polarization is the response of the citizens and outcome to the initially triggered elite polarization. Nevertheless, as Figure 3 indicates, at a more regional and European level, the scores of political polarization are not that extreme compared to Hungary, Russia, Belarus, or even Serbia and Romania.

Figure 3

Source: V-Dem data set version 13

3.4 A short stint of an anti-political establishment party 2007-2013

The loss of the 2005 elections by the Socialist Party led to a change in the party's leadership. The Socialists elected as their party chairman "an anti-communist intellectual that had never been a member of the PLA" (Kajsiu 2016, p. 290). Since the electoral campaign for local elections in 2007, the new SP leadership distanced itself from the existing political establishment, aiming to forge a political divide between the citizens and the established political elite, whose members the new leadership has been since the late 1990s. In this respect, the SP was transformed as part of a political strategy for a short period into an anti-political establishment party "appropriating a discourse of anti-politics" (Kajsiu 2016, p. 246). The intention was to maintain political polarization by only pitting the citizens against the political elite (see Schedler 1996) and presenting a public image of a non-political citizen outside the existing party system. To fully quote the remarks made by Kajsiu on this not-so-exceptional transformation of the SP into an anti-political establishment party: "This same anti-politics discourse was taken to an unprecedented extreme during the 2009 parliamentary elections, when the leader of the SP, an important actor in the Albanian post-communist political scene for twelve years, insisted that he was not a politician but a citizen." (2016, p. 246). This political strategy of inducing political polarization did not make the SP more tolerant, cooperative with the opponent, or pluralistic in its understanding of society. The outcome of the 2009 parliamentary elections, which produced a coalition government be-

tween the DP and the center-left splinter party Socialist Movement for Integration (SMI), led to a spiral of contested elections and political violence. However, the anti-political strategy of political polarization appeared not electorally rewarding for the SP, which led the party to revert to the usual style of doing politics in Albania.

4. In place of conclusion: Making political polarization recede 2005 and 2013 parliamentary elections

In both these elections, the opposition did not contest the electoral outcome of the elections, the Socialists in 2005 and the Democrats in 2013. What makes these two elections unique despite their differences is the political parties' attempt, primarily by the opposition, to structure political competition along programmatic lines. The 2005 parliamentary elections were "one of the fairest elections Albania had ever experienced" (Fischer 2010, p. 437). According to Feilcke-Tiemann the relevance of the 2005 elections, which also constituted its breakthrough, was "...the acceptance of the results by all political parties" (2006, p. 28). This applied as well to the 2013 parliamentary elections. The factors that abated political polarization in the 2005 parliamentary elections, besides the programmatic competition, was the intermediation of the international community, the European Union, more precisely that after the 2001 contested and flawed parliamentary elections urged the major political parties to reach a consensus in the election of the president of the republic in 2002. Two initially polarizing figures, such as Nano and Berisha, avoided the polarizing rhetoric and strategy and contributed to "a phase of stability and created the conditions for continuing and deepening transformation toward a market economy" (Feilcke-Tiemann 2006, p. 27).

The less polarizing strategy of the opposition in 2005 was not conditioned that much by the split within the center-left Socialist Party. On the other hand, the DP seeking broader societal support (2006, p. 27) allowed for a more pluralist behavior by incorporating within the existing DP of 2005 previous representatives of splinter parties from the DP of moderate persuasion. On the other hand, the Democratic Party also appealed to civil society organizations. It forged a temporary yet helpful cooperation with Mjaft and civic organizations that devised strategies against corruption.

In the 2013 parliamentary elections, the SP replaced the unruly anti-political establishment strategy and behavior with a more center-left programmatic competition and became more inclined to use institutional means of access to power. Moreover, the Socialist Party and its leadership ran an electoral campaign to overcome the so-called north-south divide in Albania and provide party cues and endorsements of meritocracy and inclusive policy-making in and on behalf of the state institutions. On a different note, besides the existing experience of making political polarization recede within the Albanian political dynamics, one could suggest, as potential remedies for political polarization, the introduction of institutional variables and mechanisms that encourage political moderation and consensus in the political system.

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